

POPLAR FIBER AS A NATURAL FIBROUS SORBENT FOR OIL-WATER SEPARATION

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Abstract: Natural fibers that are abundant, low-cost and biodegradable have broad potential applications in the range of oil absorption and oil/water separation. Of them, fibers with hollow structure and waxy surface, such as kapok, milkweed and poplar fibers, were mostly used to clean up oil spills [1]. In this study, diesel oil was examined to evaluate the potential of poplar seed hair fiber as an oil sorbent material. Poplar exhibits exceptional features including high hydrophobic–oleophilic property and large lumen (as shown in Figure 1). Critical parameters such as surface static contact angle and oil-water separation efficiency are examined. Poplar fibers demonstrate outstanding hydrophobic properties with a static contact angle of $153 \pm 3.7^\circ$, while exhibiting excellent lipophilicity with a static contact angle of 0° against engine oil. It is found that poplar fibers show an exceptional oil-water separation performance to remove oil from contaminated wastewater. This study presents a promising bio-based solution for mitigating water pollution caused by oil spills and other accidents, offering a low-cost, environmental-benign, and efficient approach. Moreover, poplar is a natural and biodegradable fiber that offers ease of disposal after use without causing harm to the environment.

Keywords: oil-water emulsion, separation, diesel oil, sorption capacity, poplar

1 INTRODUCTION

Oil pollution in water is a significant global environmental issue and quick cleanup of water is essential after an oil spill occurs. Oil can be removed by several processes but the most efficient method is using fibrous materials [1]. In this context, replacing synthetic fibers like polypropylene with natural materials such as poplar or milkweed can enhance the efficiency of treatment. In recent years, poplar and milkweed fibers gained increasing attention as an oil-absorbent material due to hollow structure and hydrophobic properties [2]. The object of our study is use of poplar and milkweed fibers in wet-laid fabric form and examine the impact of fiber properties and packing density on oil separation efficiency.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Poplar seed fiber and milkweed fiber were used in this study. The poplar fibers were collected and cleaned manually. Milkweed fibers were donated by Pangai Materials Science, Italy. Characteristics of fibers were stated in Table 1 (as stated in our previous studies [2,3])

Table 1 Characteristics of poplar and milkweed fibers.

Property	Poplar fiber	Milkweed fiber
Diameter	$9.1 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{m}$	$25 \pm 3.7 \mu\text{m}$
Length	$3.3 \pm 0.7 \text{ mm}$	$2.1 \pm 1.4 \text{ mm}$
Hollowness	$82 \pm 0.03 \%$	$90 \pm 0.04\%$

Diesel oil with density of 0.85 g/cm^3 , a viscosity of 10 cP, and surface tension of 30 mN/m was used for the study.

2.2 Preparation of oil/water emulsions

The oil/water emulsion was prepared by mixing 50 ml of diesel with 50 ml tap water in a 100 ml glass flask using a stirrer operated at 120 rpm for 10 min. After agitation, the diesel reached the water surface to form an oil layer.

2.3 Production of nonwovens

The nonwovens produced using the wet-laid method. In this context, 1 g of fiber sample was dispersed in 300 ml water for 10 min with a high speed blender. Then the slurry was vacuumed using laboratory setup. The laboratory setup includes a Gooch funnel, a Buchner flask along with a vacuum pump. After the suction process, the fibrous web was dried in vacuum oven at 60°C . The produced wet-laid samples of poplar fiber was coded as P and milkweed samples as MW. The steps followed to produce the samples were demonstrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Wet-laid nonwoven production.

A set of P and MW samples were further processed using a hot press equipment for compression at 130°C for 1 min (Figure 1e). These hot-pressed samples of poplar and milkweed wet-laid nonwovens were coded as HP-P and HP-MW, respectively.

2.4 Filtration Experiment

The self-made experimental setup used to separate oil from the oil-water emulsion was depicted in Figure 2.

Wet-laid nonwovens (P, MW, HP-P and HP-MW) were weighed and placed into a Gooch funnel with a diameter of 95 mm. Subsequently, prepared diesel/water emulsion was slowly poured on the surface of nonwoven sample. The nonwoven was soaked in emulsion for 180 sec, then removed and laid on a Buchner funnel. After allowing the free oil to drip naturally for 120 sec, the nonwovens were weighed.

Figure 2 Experimental setup for oil/water separation (a), Buchner funnel used to rest for 10 minutes to allow the free oil to drip out.

The oil sorption capacity (Q , g-oil/g-sorbent) of the sorbents were determined using the Equation (1):

$$Q = \frac{M_w - M_i}{M_i} \quad (1)$$

where, M_w (g) is the weight of the sorbent after immersion and M_i (g) is the initial weight of sorbent.

2.5 Characterizations

The morphological analysis of samples were examined using SEM (TESCAN VEGA3) after coated with Au/Pd for 3 min. Water contact angle of samples were measured using ThetaLite Optical Tensiometer TL 101.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Poplar fibers are very similar to milkweed fiber in terms of the appearance and morphological properties. The SEM images in Figure 3 depict the hollow structure of poplar and milkweed fibers. Fiber diameters were 9.1 μm and 25 μm for poplar and milkweed fibers, respectively (as given in Table 1). Moreover, Figure 3 illustrates that the wall thickness of poplar fiber accounts for about 18% of the total fiber diameter, while in milkweed fiber the wall thickness accounts for about 10% of the total fiber diameter. This significant lumen size is advantageous for oil sorption properties [4,5].

Figure 3 SEM images of hollow poplar(a) and milkweed fibers(b).

Besides, the outer surface coated with wax, indicates a hydrophobic property with water contact angle of up to $153 \pm 3.7^\circ$ for both poplar and milkweed floss.

The device for oil-water separation (adapted from the study of [7]) was depicted in Figure 2. As demonstrated in the Figure 2a, for P and MW nonwovens, water rapidly passed through the fiber layer, while diesel was effectively adsorbed by the poplar and milkweed fiber layer. After filtration, the filtered liquid was collected in a glass beaker, and the absence of oily layer surface on the filtered water indicated that the poplar and milkweed fibers had a high oil–water separation efficiency (as stated in the literature [1,4,5]). In addition, the fact that the volume of the water component did not decrease supported the complete absorption of diesel by the fibers. After the removal of free oil following the filtration process, it was observed that the oil absorbency of poplar fiber based was 12% and 8% higher than milkweed fibers for fibrous and hot-pressed nonwovens, respectively (Figure 4). This differences might be arose from the differences in fiber diameters. A similar

result was also obtained by Thilagavathi et al. (2018) in the use of different fibrous filters.

The filtration process depends on the properties of the oil and fibers used, as well as the packing density. As shown in Figure 4, high packing density of hot-pressed samples resulted in a reduction in oil absorption capacity by 75% (similar as conducted by Lim and Huang, 2007).

Figure 4 Diesel sorption capacities of nonwovens.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Diesel/water separation of poplar fibers was studied and compared with that of short milkweed fiber. The efficiency of oil separation was examined in terms of fiber properties and packing density. It was observed that the separation efficiency increased with decreasing fiber diameter and packing density. Hence, fibrous poplar web (P) provided the highest filtration performance with the combination of 9.1 μm diameter and lowest packing density. Based on experimental results, it can be concluded that the poplar fiber can be effectively used in separation of oil/water emulsions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: This research is based upon work supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TUBITAK) under Grants No. 121M308. In addition, additional support is provided by the European Commission Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Program, the SMARTWASTE, under Grant Agreement ID: 101086258.

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